

***Zelus renardii* (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae): first records from Croatia, Montenegro, and an accidental introduction to the Czech Republic**

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Abstract. Based on the collected specimen and available photographs, we provide first records of the invasive assassin bug species *Zelus (Diplodacus) renardii* Kolenati, 1857 from Croatia and Montenegro. We also report a case of accidental introduction of a larva of *Z. renardii* to the Czech Republic. These records document further spreading of this species native in America in Mediterranean Europe and possible ways of its spreading to the new areas.

Key words: Hemiptera, Heteroptera, Reduviidae, Harpactorinae, alien species, Croatia, Czech Republic, Montenegro, Palaearctic Region

Introduction

The assassin bug genus *Zelus* Fabricius, 1803, member of the family Reduviidae, the subfamily Harpactorinae, and the tribe Harpactorini, includes 71 species distributed in the New World, from southern Canada to central Argentina (Froeschner 1988; Maldonado-Capriles 1990; Zhang et al. 2016). Only two species of *Zelus* have been recorded in the Old World: *Z. (Zelus) longipes* (Linnaeus, 1767) with doubtful records from Iran (Sakenin et al. 2008, as *Z. biblobus* [sic!], instead of *Z. bilobus* (Say, 1832)); Ghahari et al. 2013), and *Z. (Diplodacus) renardii* Kolenati, 1857¹⁾, recently introduced to the Mediterranean (see below).

Zelus renardii is native to the Western and Southwestern United States of America (USA) and northern Central America. Zhang et al. (2016) provided confirmed records from USA: Arizona, Arkansas, California, Colorado, Nevada, New Mexico, Oklahoma, Oregon, Texas, Utah, most of Mexico, Guatemala, Honduras, and El Salvador. It was listed also from Louisiana and Jamaica (Froeschner 1988; Maldonado-Capriles 1990) though not confirmed by Hart (1987) and Zhang et al. (2016). Within its native range, *Z. renardii* inhabits areas of tropical, arid and semi-arid, as well as Mediterranean climate (Weirauch et al. 2012).

The species has been introduced to Hawaiian Islands already in 19th century, being first found at Honolulu in 1897 and described as a new species, *Z. peregrinus* Kirkaldy, 1902 (Kirkaldy 1902, 1908, 1910; Zimmerman 1948).

Later, it was discovered also in Johnston Atoll (1320 km SW of Honolulu, 1932 – Hart 1986; Zhang et al. 2016: Appendix; probably misinterpreted as Midway Atoll in Froeschner 1988), Samoa (no details – Hart 1986; Froeschner 1988; Maldonado-Capriles 1990; not confirmed by Zhang et al. 2016), French Polynesia (Tuamotu, 1971 – Zhang et al. 2016), Chile (2000 – Curkovic et al. 2004; Elgueta & Carpintero 2004, misidentified as *Z. cervicalis*; Faúndez 2015; Melo & Faúndez 2015), Argentina (2012 – D'Hervé et al. 2018; Carpintero et al. 2019), Philippines (no details – Hart 1986; Froeschner 1988; Maldonado-Capriles 1990; not confirmed by Zhang et al. 2016), and the Mediterranean (Fig. 1).

First European records came from 2010, when it was found nearly simultaneously in Athens agglomeration, Greece (Davranoglou 2011; Petrakis & Moulet 2011) and Monteagudo in Murcia, Spain (Baena & Torres 2012; Vivas 2012). Further records of the species in northern and eastern Mediterranean followed soon, documenting its rapid spread in mainland Italy (2013 – Dioli 2013), Crete (2014 – van der Heyden 2015), Asian and European Turkey (2015 and 2016, respectively – Çerçi & Koçak 2016), Albania (2016 – van der Heyden 2017), Israel (2018 – van der Heyden 2018), France (2019 – Garrouste 2019), Portugal (2020 – van der Heyden & Grosso-Silva 2020), Sardinia (2020 – Rattu & Dioli 2020), and Sicily (2020 – Bella 2020). Finally, in 2021 the species was found in Tenerife, Canary Islands (Baena & Santos 2021a; van der Heyden 2022) and Black Sea coast of Romania (Preda in prep.) (for details see Table 1).

¹⁾ In some papers, the year of publication of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati is given as 1856 (e.g., Froeschner 1988; Zhang et al. 2016, partim). However, the censor's note permitting print of the volume 29 of the *Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou* gives the date February 28, 1857 [= March 12, 1857 of Gregorian calendar]. 1857 was accepted as the correct year of publication for example by Hart (1986), Maldonado Capriles (1990), Aukema et al. (2013), Zhang et al. (2016, partim) and Baena & Santos (2021a,b). Aukema et al. (2013) listed the authorship of the species as *Z. renardii* (Kolenati [sic!], 1857), however, as the original combination was *Zelus renardii* (see Kolenati 1857), the author's name should not be given in parentheses: *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857.

Fig. 1. Distribution of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 in the Mediterranean. (Map created using: <https://www.simplemappr.net/>).

There are also isolated indoor records from Germany, Denmark, and England (van der Heyden 2021a,b) which illustrate the human mediated pathways of its spreading. The citations of its occurrence in Algeria and Lybia by Bella (2020) seems to be erroneous (see Baena & Santos 2021a).

As a newcomer in Euro-Mediterranean, the genus *Zelus* is missing from the identification monograph of Putshkov & Moulet (2009). Within the fauna of this region, *Z. renardii* resembles most the species of the genus *Nagusta* Stål, 1859 (see Putshkov & Moulet 2009: 286). However, those are usually either smaller (7.0–11.5 mm in *N. nigerensis* Villiers, 1948, *N. simonis* Puton, 1890, *N. tuberosa* Stål, 1874 – Putshkov & Moulet 2009) or larger (12.5–16.2 mm in *N. goedelii* (Kolenati, 1857) – Putshkov & Moulet 2009) than *Z. renardii* (10.57–12.98 mm according to Zhang et al. 2016) and further differ by presence of spines on antenniferous tubercles, spinose humeral angles of pronotum, laterally produced connexival segments, as well as usually uniform brown colouration of entire body and its appendices (see Putshkov & Moulet 2009). In *Z. renardii* the antenniferous tubercles are devoid of spines, humeral angles of pronotum are acutangulate but not spinose, connexival segments are not expanded laterally, and body ventrally and femora are greenish (in dead specimens yellowish).

In California, *Z. renardii* is common in suburban and disturbed habitats in addition to certain natural areas (ranging from 8 to 2000 meter above sea level). In suburban environments it was frequently found on native and non-native herbaceous and woody plants, as well as on vegetable (tomatoes, pepper).

Fig. 2. Habitus photo of male *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 collected in Žuljana, Croatia (body length 11.85 mm).

It often occurs on flowering vegetation that attracts a diversity of potential prey (Weirauch et al. 2012, van der Heyden 2015). It was also collected in alfalfa fields in Arizona (Rakickas & Watson 1974, Cohen & Tang 1997) and cotton fields in California and Texas (Ables 1978; Cisneros & Rosenheim 1997, 1998). Ables (1978) reported unusually high population densities (50,000–75,000 specimens per hectare) of *Z. renardii* in some untreated cotton fields.

Zelus renardii is a generalist predator known to prey on adults, larvae as well as eggs of various groups of insects (thrips, aphids, psyllids, leafhoppers, true bugs, lacewings, hymenopterans, beetles, mosquitoes, flies), spiders and spider mites (Kirkaldy 1910; Zimmerman 1948; Ables 1978; Mbata et al. 1987; Cohen & Tang 1997; Cisneros & Rosenheim 1997, 1998; Law & Sediqi 2010; Petrakis & Moulet 2011; Weirauch et al. 2012; van der Heyden 2017; D'Hervé et al. 2018; Rodríguez Lozano et al. 2018; Garrouste 2019; Goula et al. 2019; Bella 2020; Çelik et al. 2021; Özgen et al. 2021, Lahbib et al. 2022).

According to Lahbib et al. (2022), it prefers comparatively large, highly mobile, and readily available prey. *Zelus renardii* seems to prefer hemipteran prey (namely leafhoppers, aphids and psyllids). It often seeks honeydew-contaminated plants because they may host potential prey, however it shows no interest in immotile instars of whiteflies and scale insects (Lahbib et al. 2022).

With its congeners it shares a unique predation technique of 'sticky trap predation' involving use of sticky substances coated on its fore and middle legs; while adults and older larval instars secrete these substances from their dermal glands, the first instars instead obtain them from empty egg shells (Law & Sediqi 2010, Weirauch et al. 2012, Zhang & Weirauch 2013). These sticky substances increase predation success and also enhance the bug's adherence to the substrate (Law & Sediqi 2010). The females glue their egg batches on plants (usually on the under surface of the leaves) or other objects (e.g. tissue paper in the lab) (Weirauch et al. 2012). Stoner et al. (1975) studied the ability of plant-feeding in first instars, however, though it prolonged their survival compared to feeding on only water, it did not allow their development on such a diet. Additional details on feeding biology, mating and development of *Z. renardii* could be found in Ables (1978), Mbata et al. (1987), Cohen (1993), Cohen & Tang (1997), Cisneros & Rosenheim (1997, 1998), Law & Sediqi (2010), and Lahbib et al. (2022). This species may cause a bite to humans (Rodríguez Lozano et al. 2018, Pérez-Gómez et al. 2020, Baena & Santos 2021a, Miralles-Núñez et al. 2021, Lahbib et al. 2022).

Material examined

CROATIA: Splitsko-Dalmatinska County: Jelsa, approx. 43.117168°N 16.699025°E, viii.2021, 1 adult, photographic record (fot. „albertcardona“, available at: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/92134125>).

Dubrovacko-Neretvanska County: Općina Mljet, 42.699968°N 17.739982°E, 8.ix.2021, 1 adult, photographic record (fot. „skejo“, available at: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/94919700>); Pelješac Peninsula, Žuljana, Vučine bay, 42.887271°N 17.449646°E, campsite, 24.ix.2021, 1 male (Fig. 2), J. Balážová lgt., P. Kment det. (coll. National Museum, Prague, Czech Republic).

CZECH REPUBLIC: Bohemia: Plzeň, approx. 49.7413889°N, 13.3825000°E, 7.xii.2019, 1 larva, probably arrived in crate of tangerines, photographed by M. Opielová, L.-R. Davranoglou det.

MONTENEGRO: Tivat, 42.430503°N 18.704392°E, 28.ix.2020, 1 larva, photographic record (fot. „kishmish“, available at: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/61765746>).

Discussion

Since 2010, *Z. renardii* is spreading quickly in northern and eastern Mediterranean. In this non-native area, this species is found usually in urban, suburban and rural areas on native as well as non-native trees and shrubs (e.g., *Ailanthus altissima*, *Aloysia citriodora*, *Brachychiton populneus*, *Buxus sempervirens*, *Chamaerops humilis*, *Citrus* spp., *Corylus avellana*, *Cupressus*, *Eucalyptus*, *Ficus* spp., *Hedera helix*, *Laurus nobilis*, *Malus*, *Nerium oleander*, *Olea europaea*, *Paulownia*, *Pinus*, *Pitosporum tobira*, *Pyraecantha coccinea*, *Pyrus communis*, *Quercus ilex*, *Salix*, *Spartium junceum*, *Vitis*), as well as herbs (e.g. *Capsicum* spp., *Chenopodium nepeta*, *Daucus carota*, *Mentha*, *Lantana camara*, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Plectranthus*, *Teucrium*), often on ruderal vegetation (Davranoglou 2010; Petrakis & Moulet 2011; van der Heyden 2015, 2017; Çerçi & Koçak 2016; Simov et al. 2017; D'Hervé et al. 2018; Pinzari et al. 2018; Rodríguez Lozano et al. 2018; Goula et al. 2019; Bella 2020; Kıyak 2020; Pérez-Gómez et al. 2020; Baena & Santos 2021a; Lahbib et al. 2022).

This is in agreement with its habitat requirements in California as described by Weirauch et al. (2012). Moreover, the species is frequently encountered in houses (Faúndez 2015, D'Hervé et al. 2018, Rodríguez Lozano et al. 2018, Dursun & Fent 2020, Baena & Santos 2021a) where it may hibernate (Dioli 2013); it was also found in car parking (Pérez-Gómez et al. 2020) or camping site (this paper).

All the four records from non-Mediterranean Europe were made indoor, the Czech one suggests the import of the specimen with exotic fruits (van der Heyden 2021a,b; this paper). Considering the dispersal pathways, Davranoglou (2011) and Weirauch et al. (2012) suggested that egg batches may be easily shipped with nursery stock but despite this pathway seems likely, we lack evidence to support it. On the other hand, the above mentioned records document hitchhiking of adults and larvae which is not surprising in species frequently occurring in synanthropic conditions, being moreover attracted to light (Faúndez 2015, Simov et al. 2017).

Table 1. Chronological review of the spread of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 in Europe and the Mediterranean.

Country	Region	Year of first record	Reference	
Greece	Attica	2010	Davranoglou (2011), Petrakis & Moulet (2011)	
	Achaea	2014	Simov et al. (2017)	
	Crete	2014	van der Heyden (2015)	
	Aetolia-Acarmania	2015	Simov et al. (2017)	
	Thessaly	2015	Simov et al. (2017)	
Spain	Murcia	2010	Baena & Torres (2012), Vivas (2012)	
	Cádiz	2013	Pérez-Gómez et al. (2020)	
	Granada	2016	Pérez-Gómez et al. (2020)	
	Málaga	2016	Pérez-Gómez et al. (2020)	
	Almería	2017	Rodríguez-Lozano et al. (2018)	
	Alicante	2018	Rodríguez-Lozano et al. (2018), Miralles-Núñez et al. (2021), Lahbib et al. (2022)	
	Barcelona	2018	Goula et al. (2019)	
	Castellon	2018	Goula et al. (2019)	
	Sevilla	2018	Goula et al. (2019)	
	Madrid	2019	Goula et al. (2019)	
	Valencia	2019	Goula et al. (2019)	
	Albacete	2020	Baena & Santos (2021a)	
	Cuenca	2020	Baena & Santos (2021a)	
	Gerona	2020	Baena & Santos (2021a)	
	Islas Baleares: Mallorca	2020	Baena & Santos (2021a)	
	Tarragona	2020	Baena & Santos (2021a)	
	Badajoz	2021	Baena & Santos (2021a)	
	Italy	Lazio	2013	Dioli (2013)
		Apulia	2014	Cornara et al. (2016), Pinzari et al. (2018), Lahbib et al. (2022)
Campania		2020	Bella (2020)	
Liguria		2020	Bella (2020)	
Sardinia		2020	Rattu & Dioli (2020)	
Sicily		2020	Bella (2020)	
Turkey: Asian part	İzmir	2015	Çerçi & Koçak (2016)	
	Aydın	2016	Çerçi et al. (2021)	
	Muğla	2016	Çerçi et al. (2021)	
	Amasya	2018	Dursun & Fent (2020), Dursun (2021)	
	Balıkesir	2018	Çerçi et al. (2021)	
	Bursa	2018	Çerçi et al. (2021)	
	Yalova	2018	Çerçi et al. (2021)	
	Antalya	2019	Çerçi et al. (2021)	
	Çanakkale	2019	Çerçi et al. (2021)	
	Denizli	2019	Çerçi et al. (2021)	
	Manisa	2019	Çerçi et al. (2021)	
	Ankara	2020	Kiyak (2020)	
	Çorum	2020	Dursun (2021)	
	Diyarbakır	2020	Çelik et al. (2021)	
Eskişehir	2021	Çerçi et al. (2021)		
Turkey: European part	İstanbul	2016	Çerçi & Koçak (2016)	
Albania	Vlorë	2016	van der Heyden (2017)	
	Tirana	2019	Lahbib et al. (2022)	
Israel	North District	2018	van der Heyden (2018)	
Czech Republic	Bohemia	2019	this paper	
France	Var	2019	Garrouste (2019)	
Denmark	North Jutlandic Island	2020	van der Heyden (2021b) (accidental introduction)	
Germany	Baden-Württemberg	2020	van der Heyden (2021a,b) (accidental introduction)	
Montenegro	Tivat	2020	this paper	
Portugal	Algarve	2020	van der Heyden & Grosso-Silva (2020)	
United Kingdom: England	Cumbria	2020	van der Heyden (2021b) (accidental introduction)	
Canary Islands	Tenerife	2021	Baena & Santos (2021a), van der Heyden (2022)	
Croatia	Splitsko-Dalmatinska County, Dubrovacko-Neretvanska County	2021	this paper	
Romania	Constanța County	2021	Preda (in prep.)	

It should be mentioned that frequent synanthropic occurrence and seeking indoor hibernation sites is characteristic also for other very successful heteropteran invaders, *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (e.g., Blatt 1994, Fent & Kment 2011) and *Halyomorpha halys* (Stål, 1855) (Pentatomidae) (e.g., Inkley 2012; Hamilton et al. 2018; Nixon et al. 2021). Further predisposition for successful spreading may be the ability of *Z. renardii* to survive well in adverse circumstances such as hot conditions and irregular food supply (Butler 1966; Ali & Watson 1978; Weirauch et al. 2012). Weirauch et al. (2012) also ascertained high percentage (67%) of hatching viable first instars, however, results of Mbata et al. (1987) do not confirm this, so its influence on possible spreading success remains a question.

Acknowledgements

The first author is obliged to Miss Julie Balážová (Letonice, Czech Republic) for donation of the collected specimen from Croatia. We also thank M. Opielová (Plzeň, Czech Republic) for sending us her photograph of *Z. renardii* larva, and Leonidas-Romanos Davranoglou (Department of Zoology, University of Oxford, United Kingdom) for its identification, and Cristina Preda (Constanța, Romania) for information about the first record in Romania. This work received support from the Ministry of the Culture of the Czech Republic (DKRVO 2019–2023/5.I.d, National Museum, 00023272).

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Received: 3 January 2022

Accepted: 14 March 2022